

Impact of Corporate Social Irresponsibility on Management Efficiency: Evidence from an Emerging Market

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Abstract: The study aims to analyse the relationship between corporate social irresponsibility (CSiR) and management efficiency as proxied by the asset turnover ratio. The study examines a sample of Indian manufacturing firms from 2007-2016 with 1,113 observations using a comprehensive dataset from RepRisk® and Bloomberg® to run a system generalized method of moments (GMM) estimation. CSiR positively affects management efficiency and the effective utilization of assets in generating sales. For domestically focused manufacturing companies in emerging economies with less demand or stakeholder expectation, corporate irresponsibility may not be as important a deciding factor, especially if the target market is highly price sensitive. However, managers should heed caution before divulging in CSiR activities, for the consequences can be damaging in the long run. The study's grounding in an emerging market setting, such as India, sparks a discussion on a contextualized understanding of negative aspects of corporate behavior in evaluating the management efficiency of the firm.

Keywords: ESG issues, Corporate Social Irresponsibility, Management Efficiency, Reputational Shocks, Emerging Markets

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1. Introduction

The philosophy of profit maximization may not always hold companies accountable to society (Jensen, 2002). The agency-capitalist system dictates the board as owner's representatives and agents. Management is incentivized to maximize profits at any cost, even if it means engaging in socially irresponsible behavior, as long as they avoid charges (Campbell, 2007). Thus, corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become meaningless and ironic. Motivated by personal and company interests, management and shareholders may sanction, support, and accept corporate social irresponsibility (CSiR) and its benefits, such as competitive edge and lower manufacturing cost (Banerjee, 2008).

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Indian manufacturing companies are frequently required to participate in CSR, and inclusive, sustainable evaluation and verification may affect social and environmental risk avoidance, efficiency, and credibility. Manufacturing firms require large investments (Seth et al., 2021), so effective management is needed to meet their funding and social responsibility needs. Studies on developed economies dominate extant literature. Since cultural and social factors affect how people understand CSR in different situations, how CSiR impacts the managerial efficiency of manufacturing firms in emerging economies is even less clear. Emerging economies question the "Americanized" meaning of CSR. For instance, India and China prominently associate CSR with philanthropy and charity (Arora and Puranik, 2004; Matten and Moon, 2008), and are less likely to embrace issues like sustainability, ethical business practices, and good governance. Similarly, the mere definition of CSiR differs in the context of developed and emerging economy.

Stakeholders around the world condemn the irresponsible actions of manufacturing companies. However, corporate irresponsibility may be less important for domestically focused manufacturing companies in emerging economies, where demand and stakeholder expectations are lower, especially if the target market is highly price sensitive. Senior executives express concern that improved sustainability standards may negatively affect profitability and competitiveness because they demand resource commitment (Nidumolu et al., 2009). Nonetheless, CSiR poses a significant negative, ongoing, and protracted impact on a company's reputation, stakeholder relationships, and financial performance (Lange and Washburn, 2012; Kang et al., 2016; Price and Sun, 2017). The study examines the relationship between CSiR and management efficiency in an emerging market's (India) manufacturing sector. We address CSiR as a distinct construct from CSR, and our results indicate institutional viewpoints and strategic use of CSiR.

2. Literature Review

Numerous studies recognize the importance of CSR; however, studies defining CSiR are limited (Muller and Kräussl, 2011; Kotchen and Moon, 2012; Lange and Washburn, 2012). Following the definition of CSR, corporate social irresponsibility is described as "the actions of the firm negatively affecting a social stakeholder's evident claims in the long run" (Strike et al., 2006, p. 852). Throughout the well-researched literature on CSR (Arora and Puranik, 2004; Hasan et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021), the impact of irresponsible behavior of the firms are much less explored (Lioui and Sharma, 2012; Lin-Hi and Muller, 2013). Kang et al. (2016) used structural panel vector auto-regression to test slack resources, good management, penance, and insurance mechanisms and model the relationship between CSR, CSiR, and firm performance. Their study concluded that the firm's irresponsible act often precedes the responsible one, and CSR does not effectively set off the effects of CSiR. Kotchen and Moon (2012) examined a panel dataset

of 3000 companies from 1991-2005 and concluded that more CSiR resulted in more CSR. Strike et al. (2006) and Walker et al. (2016) examined the simultaneous impact of a firm's responsible and irresponsible behavior on its performance. Both studies concluded that firms lose value when they engage in CSiR. The study by Price and Sun (2017) concluded that irresponsible activities have a lasting effect on firm performance than responsible activities. Further, firms engaged in low levels of CSR and CSiR activities fare better than firms undertaking high levels of CSR and CSiR activities. Walker et al. (2019) studied the effects of CSiR on the performance of firms in coordinated market economies (CMEs) and liberal market economies (LMEs). They observed the engagement of CME firms in CSiR lower than LME firms and a negative correlation between CSiR and firm performance in LMEs but not CMEs. Thus, we hypothesize:

H1: Corporate social irresponsibility is negatively related to management efficiency.

3. Data and Method

3.1. Data

The dataset is compiled using the following databases: RepRisk[®] provided data for corporate social irresponsibility, while Bloomberg[®] provided firm-level information. The sample consists of all the Indian manufacturing firms available in RepRisk[®]. We eliminated firms with yearly observations of less than two years. The final sample yielded a total of 185 manufacturing firms, and analysis was carried out on the sample containing 1,113 firm-year observations from 2007 to 2016.

3.2. Variables

Corporate Social Irresponsibility: RRI is an index ranging from 0-100 and signifies the current level of reputational risk pertaining to environmental, social, and governance issues. The higher the value, the higher the risk. The values are taken at a one-year lag. *Turnover Ratio:* Following the approach of Walker *et al.* (2016), we take the asset turnover ratio as the proxy measure for management efficiency. The ratio is computed by dividing sales revenue by total assets. It further reflects the firm's ability to effectively use its assets to generate revenue and measure overall company performance.

Control Variables: Following extant literature, several control variables are included. Firm size (computed as the natural log of total assets) is expected to have a negative sign. Operating profit margin (calculated by dividing EBIT with sales) and liquidity (measured as cash divided by total assets) are expected to have a positive sign. R&D ratio (calculated by dividing R&D expenses by total assets) and tangibility (calculated by dividing net property, plant, and equipment by total assets) are also expected to relate positively to management efficiency. Lastly, we introduce time dummies to control for time effects.

3.3. Method

The static and dynamic regression models are as follows:

$$\text{Turnover Ratio}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{CSiR}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{Size}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Tangibility}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{Profit}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{Liquidity}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{R\&D}_{i,t} + \text{Industry Dummies} + \text{Time Dummies} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Turnover Ratio}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Turnover Ratio}_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{CSiR}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Size}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{Tangibility}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{Profit}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{Liquidity}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{R\&D}_{i,t} + \text{Industry Dummies} + \text{Time Dummies} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{2}$$

Where, the Turnover Ratio serves as a proxy measure for management efficiency and effective utilization of assets. CSiR is an explanatory variable followed by control variables, as described previously. *i* and *t* depict firm *i* at *t*th year, respectively. All variables were winsorized at the top and bottom 1 per cent tails to reduce the influence of outliers and maintain the premise of normality (Suman and Singh, 2020). Equation (1) depicts our static model, and to analyse it, we employ the fixed effects model and pooled ordinary least squares (OLS). The Bruesch-Pagan test confirms the precedence of the random effects model over pooled OLS, and the Hausman test confirms the preference for the fixed effects model over the random effects model. Both were determined to be statistically significant at 1per cent. Equation (2) depicts our dynamic model, and to analyse it, we employ the two-step system GMM approach with corrected standard errors (Arellano and Bond, 1991; Blundell and Bond, 2000). Data persistence is a result of the relationship between a previous year’s management efficiency and its status in the current year. Reverse causality is another issue; rather than CSiR causing a lack of effective management, poor management results in careless corporate behaviour. Therefore, our sample contains autocorrelation and endogeneity concerns. The AR(2) test and Hansen J test are used to support the adoption of system GMM. The Hansen J test and AR (2) tests both guarantees that the instruments are exogenous and that there is no second-order autocorrelation, respectively.

4. Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the firm-level variables used in baseline regression models and robust checks. The correlation between the variables is not more than 0.54, and the mean variance inflation factor is 2.66. Hence, our data does not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Turnover	1820	0.958	0.551	0	2.275
CSiR	1926	4.21	9.157	-1	55
Size	1820	6.142	1.828	1.949	10.438
Tangibility	1706	0.558	1.231	0.003	15.387
RDratio	1432	0.009	0.019	0	0.093
Profit	1713	0.734	4.341	-0.946	38.561
Liquidity	1573	0.681	18.883	-154.23	549.937

Table 2 presents the results for pooled OLS, fixed-effects model, and system GMM regressing management efficiency on CSiR and control variables. Columns 1 and 2 indicate the results of pooled OLS and fixed-effects, respectively. Column 3 presents the results of the system GMM estimation technique and reports significant positive relation between CSiR and turnover ratio. Statistically significant lagged values indicate persistence in the asset turnover ratio. Our results indicate a positive association between CSiR and management efficiency. The findings are counter-normative to our assumptions and the extant literature (Walker *et al.*, 2016). We conducted two additional analyses* to confirm our findings. First, we introduced CSR in the model, and second, we took an alternative measure of liquidity (cash-to-sales ratio). No discernible change was observed.

Table 2: Regression Results for Turnover Ratio

Variables	(OLS)	(FE)	(GMM)
	Turnover	Turnover	Turnover
CSiR	-0.00104	0.000368	0.00479*
Profit	-0.0614*	-0.0608**	0.626
Size	-0.0783***	-0.190**	-0.0594
Tangibility	0.0291	0.0418***	-0.134
Rdratio	-0.455	-0.523	8.427
Liquidity	0.000234	-0.00407	0.562
TurnoverLag			0.905***
Constant	2.214***	2.199***	0.698
Year effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,162	1,162	1,113
R-squared	0.385	0.152	
Hansen J test			0.807
AR (2) test			0.375

Notes: The table presents the regression results for static and dynamic models. ***, ** and * denotes significance levels at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The study analyses the effect of corporate social irresponsibility on management efficiency and effective utilization of assets in generating sales. We posit that the firm’s involvement in CSiR activities indicates poor managerial efficiency and raises concerns regarding the effective use of company assets. Using a sample of Indian manufacturing firms, we tested our theoretical view on turnover ratio, a proxy measure to depict management efficiency. We found a significant positive impact of corporate irresponsibility on management efficiency. Even though the results signal a strategic use of CSiR to attain better utilization of assets to generate sales, firms should not indulge in

irresponsible activities, for it can cause severe environmental, social, and legal consequences.

This paper adds to the rapidly increasing literature on CSiR and furthers the concept by providing empirical evidence of how CSiR impacts the management efficiency of Indian manufacturing firms. Manufacturing units are often expected to indulge heavily in CSR activities, which pressure the management to generate returns to cover funding and social costs. Therefore, by analyzing the relationship between CSiR and management efficiency, this study highlights the need for an efficient managerial board and effective utilization of assets in Indian manufacturing firms. Furthermore, companies whose primary goal is to maximize profits typically align their top executives' compensation with that goal. Hence, management and shareholders are incentivized to maximize profits regardless of the social or environmental consequences as long as they are not penalized. Moreover, India is a developing economy with a lax regulatory framework. The markets are inefficient, and investors' primary concern is maximizing their returns at the expense of social responsibility or compliance with the law. Based on our findings, businesses may engage in unethical practices like using substandard materials and engaging in questionable dealings to gain an economic advantage. For the aforementioned reasons, it is not unexpected that CSiR has taken the view of a strategic tool to enhance a corporation's market potential and financial performance. However, managers should be cautious of the detrimental impact of CSiR on the firm's reputation, customer base, share price, and overall performance; and should tread carefully while divulging in morally questionable activities.

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Supplementary Analysis

To verify the robustness of our results, we undertook a couple of supplementary analyses. Table 3 depicts the summarized results. First, CSR was introduced in the model, proxied by Bloomberg's ESG disclosure scores. CSR is one of the driving forces that increases management efficiency (Silberhorn and Warron, 2007). It is also used as a strategic move to augment brand image (Bhattacharyya, 2010) and it may mitigate the deteriorating impact of CSiR. Our results were found robust to the initial findings. Second, we take alternative measure of liquidity (calculated by dividing cash by total sales). No significant difference was found from the former results.

Table 3: Supplementary analysis

	(Model 1)	(Model 2)
Variables	Turnover	Turnover
CSiR	0.00254*	0.00612*
Profit	-0.137	-0.231
Size	-0.112*	-0.0658*
Tangibility	-0.0921	0.106**
RDratio	7.748*	-0.477
Liquidity1	0.380*	
TurnoverLag	0.562***	0.712***
CSR	0.00496	
Liquidity2		0.00386
Constant	1.373**	0.914**
Year effects	Yes	Yes
Observations	879	1,113
Hansen J test	0.109	0.239
AR (2) test	0.193	0.322

Notes: The table presents the regression results conducted to check the robustness of our initial findings. ***, ** and * denotes significance levels at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.